

CONCEPTIONS OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE ASSOCIATED WITH MOTIVATIONAL APPROACH

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Professional and practice-based learning are the contexts in which the idea of competence is situated. This is a process of learning that takes many various forms. It varies according to the learners' personal traits, professional levels, practice areas, intentionality of learning, and formalization of the learning activities. This varied approach has incorporated notions of competence in a variety of ways.

The definition of competence, however, varies from the relationship between it and professional practice. Here, three major approaches to professional development and competency are distinguished:

1. Behavioristic functionalism and competence, which emphasizes the significance of precisely identifying the differences between actual and desired competence, resulting in the training of occasionally minuscule skills; a significant drawback of this method is fragmenting learning;
2. Competence as integrated occupationalism, seen in current qualification frameworks and competence-based education systems that emphasize the integration of information, skills, and attitudes in curriculum development, instruction, learning, and assessment;
3. The concept of competence as situated professionalism suggests that competence is only meaningful in a specific context. A major shortcoming in this regard is holism, which occurs when specifics of competence are covered under generalized descriptions of people's abilities, which may be adequate for personal development processes but not for professional certification requirements (Mulder, 2011).

When a professional performs in accordance with established performance standards, they do it responsibly and successfully. It is also possible to argue that this expert is sufficiently competent.

In a given professional domain, job, role, organizational context, and task situation, professional competence is defined as the general, integrated, and internalized capability to deliver sustainable effective (worthy) performance (including problem solving, realizing innovation, and creating transformation).

A variety of competencies make up competence. A competency is a coherent cluster of knowledge, abilities, and attitudes that can be used in actual

performance scenarios. Competencies are a subset of generic competence. For example, a forensic expert may be required to generate a DNA profile of an item of evidence during a crime scene investigation. This calls for disciplinary knowledge, artifact handling abilities, and integrity, accuracy, and pressure tolerance. These taken together make up professional competency. For example, flower auction dealers need to have the following knowledge: about the items, quality indicators, market trends, and prices; about multitasking, information processing, and quick decision making; and about attitudes: stress tolerance and a sense of urgency when making sales. These also constitute components of professional competence.

The meaning of competence discussed above is mainly related to professional competence, as used in key competencies, competence domains, competence clusters, enabling competencies, and competency dimensions or competency components.

To the best of our knowledge, White (1959) was the first in the psychological literature on motivation to provide the idea of competence and to conceptualize it as a crucial idea to explain behavior. Prior to that point, the idea was used more instrumentally and in relation to daily tasks rather than in a thematic manner. White expressed his dissatisfaction with Freud and other personality psychologists, who believed that "drives" was the key to understanding human behavior. Rather, he suggested that the key idea be "competence," which he defined as "...an organism's capacity to interact effectively with its environment." White (1959) emphasized studies that demonstrated behavior motivation is far more complex than simply satisfying specific impulses by using examples from biological experiments.

Youngsters, scholars, and professionals in general are driven to acquire the knowledge and abilities necessary to perform well in their surroundings. These abilities may be more or less complex phenomena. Performance motivation tests were created to measure motivation in the classroom. These tests contained questions about failure anxiety, which was found to be a significant obstacle to both the creation of educational assessments and academic success in general. Becoming competent and, thus, confident that one understands the problem and can effectively perform in a particular setting is satisfying and is still regarded as self-efficacy when a problem is complicated or a performance situation is challenging (Bandura, 1977).

In the subject of learning in general and professional learning in particular, the realization that competence is performance incentive has been crucial. It is

helpful to realize that there wouldn't be any professional learning at all if there wasn't performance motivation or the desire to acquire a particular degree of professional expertise.

Gradually, the idea of competence found its way into higher education. A series of case studies on competence-based education systems in the United States that were put into place in the 1970s was published by Grant, Elbow, Ewens, Gamson, Kohli, Neumann, Olesen, and Riesman in 1979. The US Department of Health, Education, and Welfare's Fund for the Improvement of Postsecondary Education provided funding for the case studies. The same fund assisted institutions of higher learning in reworking their courses to emphasize competence-based learning. White, McClelland, Gilbert, Grant, and others' work has made a substantial contribution to our understanding of what competence means in the context of professional learning. It demonstrates how crucial competence is for performance motivation, evaluation, performance enhancement, and innovative teaching. All of these are necessary to create high-quality professional and practice-based learning. Competence in multiple professions will be covered in the next part to make the general remarks a little more applicable. Competency models have, and continue to provide, a wealth of examples supporting professional standardization, certification, licensure, professional development, and evaluation.

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